

Disease Prediction System

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Abstract:

Accurate analysis of health problem is done for the prevention and curing the illness. Machine learning helps in getting better results of disease prediction than the traditional methods. Multiple ML algorithms are used to design a disease prediction system. We use algorithms like Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine for disease prediction.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Supervised Learning, Python, Logistic Regression Algorithm, SVM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the arrival of advanced computing, the doctors' still requires the technology in various possible ways like surgical representation process and x-ray photography, but the technology perceptually stayed behind. The method still requires the doctor's information and experience due to alternative factors starting from medical

records to weather conditions, atmosphere, blood pressure and numerous alternative factors.

. It contains four steps

The doctor gather all information about the patients and create a symptoms list.

The doctor should make a list of all possible causes of symptoms.

The doctor should prioritize the list by which is the most dangerous possible cause of symptoms put in the top of the list.

If there will be no such diagnosis means removing the diagnosis from the list and using tests that should have distinct results, depends on which diagnosis is correct.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

- Medical decision could be extremely specialized and difficult job due to alternative factors.
- The existing system includes information search method by using history of medical records. Differential diagnosis methods can be used to identify the presence of an entity where multiple alternatives are possible and also refers to include the candidate alternatives.
- In the existing system algorithms like Naïve bayes and Random Forest algorithms are used.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Logistic Regression and SVM are supervised learning algorithms which are used to solve the clustering problem. The main idea is to determine the disease and implementation of drug. Different tests performed on the patients will served as a attributes for clustering. By using this algorithm it reduce the number of iterations to produce the accurate result for each and every diagnosis. These algorithms identify the accurate disease and gives the result as the output. Supervised learning algorithms such Logistic Regression and SVM give more accurate results than other algorithms like KNN algorithms.

IV. RESULTS

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V. CONCLUSION

We have implemented this project using Logistic Regression and SVM algorithms but, it also includes other methods like Naive bayes, Random Forest internally. The accuracy of the output is resulted as 95%. There is a difference between the accuracy of weighted KNN and supervised algorithms like SVM and Logistic regression where there is more accuracy in the current process.

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